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PRECIOUS STONES IN THE ENGLISH AND THE ARMENIAN BIBLES

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Abstract

This paper attempts to present an in-depth analysis of the translation strategies adopted for biblical gemstones with the aim of determining the similarities and dissimilarities of two contrasted languages. Studying biblical gemstones in English and Armenian is remarkable not only based on linguistic significance – as they form an integral part of world literary heritage – but also on the basis of discovering the language, religion, and culture behind the contrasted languages.

Keywords: Bible, biblical gemstone, contrastive study, stylistic devices, equivalence, contrastive stylistics.

The Bible is widely recognized as the “Greatest Book” ever written. It is one of the oldest and most mysterious books comprising not only the world vision and the history of different countries but also having the power to heal and prophesy. Originating in ancient times, biblical gemstones have accompanied people in their immemorial existence, enriching and enhancing their imaginative thinking as well as the national culture.

Precious stones are stones remarkable for their colour, brilliance, or rarity. Such stones have at all times been held in high esteem everywhere, particularly in the East. The precious stones of the Bible are chiefly of interest in connection with the breastplate of the high priest (Exodus 28:17-20; 39:10-13), the treasure of the King of Tyre (Ezekiel 28:13), and the foundations of the New Jerusalem (Tobit 13:16-17, in the Greek text, and more fully, Revelation 21:18-21). The twelve stones of the breastplate and the two stones of the shoulder ornaments seem to have been considered by the Jews as the most precious; they undoubtedly serve as the standard of whatever is beautiful and rich beyond measure; both Ezekiel 28:13 and Apocalypse 21:18-21, are patterned after the model of the rational; no wonder therefore that the stones entering its composition should have been the objects of a considerable amount of literature from the fourth century. That such literature should have arisen is of its convincing proof that the identification of the stones was no easy problem to solve. (The English Revised Version Bible; The First Major English Revision of the KJV, Oxford, 1885, 2568 p.)

The Hebrews obtained gemstones from the Middle East, India, and Egypt. At the time of the Exodus, the Bible states that the Israelites took gemstones with them (Book of Exodus, iii, 22; xii, 35-36). When they were settled in the Land of Israel, they obtained gemstones from the merchant caravans traveling from Babylonia or Persia to Egypt, and those from Saba and Raamah to Tyre (Book of Ezekiel, xxvii, 22). King Solomon even equipped a fleet which returned from Ophir, laden with gems (Books of Kings, x, 11).

1. **AGATE** - The word “agate” originates from the Greek name of a stone found in the Achates River in Sicily.

This word has been translated into three different Hebrew words, and is used three times in the King James Bible and New Revised Standard Version (NRSV), and twice in the New King James Version (NKJV) and New International Version (NIV).

Known as the stabilizer, Agate is the stone to call on for support when you need stability and grounding in your life. Throughout ancient cultures, including Islamic civilizations, Babylonians, and Egyptians, Agate rock was used to protect against negative energy, which ranged in form from superstitions to tragedies and natural disasters. Agate’s soothing and stress-relieving properties help you connect with the energy of the Earth by bringing harmony to your mind, body, and spirit. When you feel unbalanced, Agate healing properties have soft vibrations that can recalibrate and realign you. [9]

Exodus

28:19 And the third row a figure, an *agate*, and an amethyst:

39:12 And the third row, a figure, an *agate*, and an amethyst:

28:19 Եւ կարգն երրորդ՝ գոճազն եւ *սկաստ* եւ սուտակ:

39:12 Եւ կարգն երրորդ՝ սուտակ եւ գոճազն եւ *սկաստ*:

Isaiah

54:12 And I will make thy windows of *agates*, and thy gates of carbuncles, and all thy borders of pleasant stones:

54:12 Եւ կանգնեցից զաշտարակս քո յասպիս, եւ զդուռնս քո յականց վանեայց. եւ ածից շուրջ զքեւ պարիսպ՝ յընտիր ընտիր *սկաստ* պատուականաց:

The word “agate”, according to “Cambridge English Dictionary” [1, p 48], implies:

1. a hard stone with strips of color, used in jewelry;
2. something made of or fitted with agate.

In English-Armenian Dictionary (Անգլերեն-հայերեն բառարան) [6: էջ 36] the word “agate” has the following translations: in Eastern Armenian ագատ, in Western Armenian սկաստ. The difference between the Eastern and Western Armenian written forms is because of the difference at phonological level. Eastern Armenian is very close to the sounds and pronunciations in Classical Armenian. Western Armenian, however, has shifted a lot of consonant sounds. Classical and Eastern Armenian maintain a 3-way distinction between voiced, voiceless unaspirated, and voiceless aspirated which can be described as a "soft", "hard" and "middle" sound for consonants. Western Armenian has a 2-way distinction, achieved with a shift from the middle sounds to the hard sound, and old hard sounds to the soft. That is why the Eastern Armenian pronunciation of the word ագատ is սկաստ in Western Armenian, which can be observed in New Western Armenian-Eastern Armenian Dictionary (Արեւմտահայերեն-արեւելահայերեն նոր բառարան [5: էջ 25]).

The word սկաստ is defined in Արդի հայերենի բացատրական բառարան [4: էջ 43] as:

1. Պոչատ, ազին՝ պոչը կտրած
2. (աստղգ.) հասարակածը և կենդանակերպը չորս հավասար մասերի բաժանող երկու մեծ բոլորակները
3. (հնք.) կվարցի գույնզգույն շերտերից բաղկացած ոչ շատ թանկագին քար

In the adduced examples, word-for-word translation, specifically, transliteration is applied. In Isa. 54:12, an attributive prepositional phrase was transferred into an attributive non-prepositional phrase. The explanation of such transference lies in the fact that English, being an analytical language by its structure, is flooded with prepositions performing the functions of declension endings. Having a highly developed declension system the relation between the words in the frame of sentences in the native language is patterned with the help of suffixes (endings).

It follows that the word under investigation is of less functional occurrence as there is a direct relationship between meaning and usage; the greater the semantic spectrum of the given word, the wider is its application (distribution).

As for the functional occurrence of the word “agate” it appears three times in the Bible.

2. **BERYL-** was one of the stones on the breastplate of the high priest (Exodus 28:20; Revised King James Version marginal note, “chalcedony;” 39:13).

In Ezek. 28:13 the Septuagint renders the word by “chrysolite,” which the Jewish historian Josephus regards as its proper translation. This also is the rendering given in the King James Version in the margin. That was a gold-colored gem, the topaz of ancient authors.

In 1220, Arnoldus Saxo recited the virtues of the beryl. In his writings, he stated the stone helped the wearer in any fight, whether it is a physical fight or litigation. Beryl made the wearer unconquerable, and somehow, also likable. Beryl also cured the wearer of the disease of laziness and empowered the wearer with sharp and quick intelligence. [9]

Exodus

28:20 And the fourth row a *beryl*, and an onyx, and a jasper: they shall be set in gold in their inclosings:

39:13 And the fourth row, *beryl*, an onyx, and a jasper: [they were] inclosed in ouches of gold in their inclosings:

10:6 His body also [was] like the *beryl*, and his face as the appearance of lightning, and his eyes as lamps of fire, and his arms and his feet like in color to polished brass, and the voice of his words like the voice of a multitude:

13:22 And the streets of Jerusalem shall be paved with *beryl* and carbuncle and stones of Ophir:

21:20 The fifth, sardonyx; the sixth, sardius; the seventh, chrysolite; the eighth, *beryl*; the ninth, a topaz; the tenth, a chrysoprasus; the eleventh, a jacinth; the twelfth, an amethyst:

The word “beryl” in “Cambridge English Dictionary” [1: p 134] is defined as “light silver-grey or sea-blue valuable stone, used in the jewelry”. As for its relative form in mother tongue stand two variants: բիւրեղ and բերիլ. The word բիւրեղ is the Western Armenian variant of the Eastern Armenian word բյուրեղ. It’s astoundingly interesting that in the Armenian dictionary we can’t find the semantic range of բերիլ. As for the semantics of բիւրեղ it implies:

1. բնականից բազմամիստ ձև ունեցող պինդ մարմին;
2. թանկագին քար՝ երկնագույն կամ դեղնասուկեգույն երակներով;
3. աչքի ծիածանաթաղանթի ետևում գտնվող երկուռուցիկ նսպանման թափանցիկ մարմին՝ վանակ, նսպնապակի;
4. յուրահատուկ փայլով՝ ճառագայթաբեկ հատկությամբ բարձրորակ ապակի:

In Exodus 28:20 and 39:13, Tobit 13:22, and Revelation 21:20 the word “beryl” is translated as բիւրեղ; being applied the technique of partial equivalence. But in Daniel 10:6 the translator skillfully applies a technique transferring the English noun “beryl” into an adjective in the target text (ծովագույն). The motivation for such conveyance lies in the fact that բիւրեղ has sky-blue color, the reflection of which we can see in the sea.

As for the functional occurrence of the word, “beryl” appears five times in the source text.

28:20 Եւ կարգն չորրորդ՝ յակինթ եւ *բիւրեղ* եւ եղունգն, ընդելուզեալ, յոսկի կապեալ՝ յիրաքանչիւր կարգս կայցեն:

39:13 Եւ կարգն չորրորդ՝ ոսկեակն եւ եղունգն եւ *բիւրեղ*. պատեալ եւ ընդելուզեալ ոսկւով:

Daniel

10:6 Եւ մարմին նորա *ծովագոյն*, եւ երեսք նորա իբրեւ զտեսիլ փայլական, եւ աչք նորա իբրեւ ճառագայթք հրոյ. բազուկք եւ բարձք նորա իբրեւ զտեսիլ փայլուն պղնձոյ, եւ բարբառ բանից նորա իբրեւ զբարբառ զօրու:

Tobit

13:22 Եւ ամենայն հրապարակքն Երուսաղեմի *բիւրեղ* եւ դահանակ եւ սարդիոնն ակամբք կազմեցին:

Revelation

21:20 հինգերորդն՝ եղնգնաքար, վեցերորդն՝ սարդիոն, եւթներորդն՝ ոսկեքար, ութերորդն՝ *բիւրեղ*, իններորդն՝ տպագիոն, տասներորդն՝ քրիստապրասու, մետասանն՝ յակինթ, երկուտասանն՝ ամեթովս:

3. **CARBUNCLE**- Hebrew: *barkath*; Septuagint: *smaragdus*; Vulgate: *smaragdus*; Revised King James Version, marginal note: “emerald”

The Hebrew word is from a root meaning “to glitter,” “lighten,” “flash.” When held up to the sun, this gem shines like a lump of burning coal, a lump of dark-red glowing coal, and hence is called “carbuncles”, i.e., a little coal. It was one of the jewels in the first row of the high priest’s breastplate. Next to the diamond, it is the hardest and most costly of all precious stones.

In older times, the carbuncle was known to be a heart stimulant. It had so much power that whoever wore the stone became passionate and angry and was at risk of having strokes. The blood-red color of the carbuncle made it a symbol of the divine sacrifice of Christ on the cross as well. Other religions have also used carbuncle for religious conceptions. The Koran says that the Fourth Heaven is composed of carbuncles. Furthermore, in many myths, the eyes of dragons are made of carbuncle.

In 1687, Enmphins wrote that a surgeon told him that he had seen a ruler on the island of Amboin with a carbuncle that was brought to him by a serpent. Supposedly, when this ruler was a child, his mother put him in a hammock hung between two trees. One day a snake crept up to him and placed a carbuncle on his body. As gratitude for this precious gift, the child's parents kept and cared for the serpent. Eventually, this particular carbuncle was in full possession of a King of Siam. [8]

Exodus

28:17 And thou shalt set in it settings of stones, [even] four rows of stones: [the first] row [shall be] a sardius, a topaz, and a **carbuncle**: [this shall be] the first row:

39:10 And they set in it four rows of stones: [the first] row [was] a sardius, a topaz, and a **carbuncle**: this [was] the first row:

54:12 And I will make thy windows of agates, and thy gates of **carbuncles**, and all thy borders of pleasant stones:

13:22 And the streets of Jerusalem shall be paved with beryl and **carbuncle**.

28:17 Եւ ընդելուզցես ի նմա ընդելուզածս, ըստ **չորեքկարգեան** ականց. կարգ ականցն, առաջին՝ զմրուխտ եւ սարդիոն եւ տպագիոն, կարգ մի:

39:10 Եւ անկաներ ընդ նմին անկուած ականակապ **չորեքկարգեան** ականց. կարգն առաջին՝ սարդիոն եւ տպագիոն եւ զմրուխտ, կարգ մի:

Isaiah

54:12 Եւ կանգնեցից զաշտարակս քո յասպիս, եւ զորունս քո յականց **վանեայց**. եւ ածից շուրջ գբել պարիսպ՝ յընտիր ընտիր ակատ պատուականաց:

Tobit

13:22 Եւ ամենայն հրապարակքն Երուսաղեմի բիրեղ եւ **դահանակ** կազմեսցին:

The semantic set of the word “carbuncle” comprises two meanings, according to “Cambridge English Dictionary” [1: p 246]:

1. a dark red precious stone;
2. a large painful swelling under the skin.

It should be noted that red is not only one of the primary colors, but it's also one of the first colors used by artists—dating back to prehistory. Ranging from orange tinges to deep wine hues, throughout history the color red has held special significance for cultures around the world. The warm color is most commonly associated with love in Western culture and remains an attractive, vibrant color that immediately brings attention to itself. In many cultures, red symbolizes joy and good fortune. In fact, in many Asian countries, brides wear red as a symbol of fertility and luck. In Europe, red became equated with aristocrats and the clergy. Its association with the blood of Christ made it especially important for the Catholic Church, so much so that the cardinal was named after the color that Roman Catholic cardinals traditionally wore. The brilliant color was favored by Ancient Romans, who used it extensively in decoration. Examples can still be seen in the wall art of Pompeii. That is why the red color has a great influence and impact on English lingua-culture. [8]

In the English-Armenian dictionary (Անգլերեն-հայերեն բառարան) [6: էջ 94] the word “carbuncle” is translated as **չորեքկարգեան**, **վանեայց** and **դահանակ**. The word **վանեայց** is the genitive case of the word **վանեայք**. And in Western Armenian its correlative forms are բյուրեղապակի, **դահանակ**.

The word **չորեքկարգեան**, according to Modern Armenian Expositive Dictionary (Արդի հայերենի բացատրական բառարան) [4: էջ 158], is defined as **չորս կողմ ունեցող կարմիր թանկարժեք քար**. The word **վանեայք** comprises two meanings:

1. Պատերի անկյուններն իրար միացնող քար, անկյունակալ;
2. (փխբ.) հիմք, հիմունք, որևէ բանի հիմնական կարևորագույն մասը.

In the Armenian Etymological Dictionary (Հայերեն ստուգաբանական բառարան), the origin of the word **վանեայք** is greek $\alpha\gamma\kappa\omega\epsilon$ unleashing the meaning անկյուն, եզր in eastern Armenian and **վանեայք**, անկիւնաքար in Western Armenian.

The word **դահանակ** is defined in Modern Armenian Expositive Dictionary (Արդի հայերենի բացատրական բառարան) Արդի հայերենի բացատրական բառարան [4: էջ 152] as:

1. Մուգ կանաչ գույնի հանք, որից պղինձ է ստացվում.
2. Այդ հանքից պատրաստված թանկագին քար.

In Exodus 28:7 and 39:10, the word “carbuncle” is rendered twice in Armenian by the means of descriptive translation, as the word **չորեքկարգեան** comprises the meaning of having four angles (**չորս կողմ ունեցող կարմիր թանկարժեք քար**). In Tobit 13:22 the word “carbuncle” is rendered once as **դահանակ** and in Isaiah 54:12 as **վանեայք**. In the last case, partial equivalence nicely fits the situation as the pragmatic meanings of the source and target language units are not the same. [3: p 76]

4. **CORAL**- Hebrew: *ramoth*, meaning “heights;” i.e., “high-priced” or valuable things, or, as some suppose, “that which grows high,” like a tree (Job 28:18; Ezek. 27:16), according to the Rabbins, red coral, which was in use for ornaments

It is found in different colors, white, black, and red. The red, being esteemed the most precious, was used, as noticed above, for ornamental purposes.

One who wears red or white coral is said to have the power to stop storms and cross wide rivers in safety. Coral was also known to stop the blood flow from a wound, provide wisdom, and cure madness.

For over twenty centuries, coral was classed as a precious stone. To be used as an amulet, coral had to be pure- meaning freshly gathered from the sea or the shore, and never worked on or engraved. If a piece of coral breaks, the pieces have no virtue or power. The stone then loses its powers and the spirit living in the stone leaves.

Peasant women hide their coral jewelry from their husbands as the stones become pale during certain seasons but then regain their bright color. The women think that the coral shares their indisposition with them. It is believed that a vital force animates coral, losing or gaining color according to specific conditions. [8]

Job

28:18 No mention shall be made of *coral*, or of pearls: for the price of wisdom [is] above rubies:

28:18 Մարջան և մարգարիտ ոչ յիշեսցին. եւ ձգեաց զիմաստութիւն քան զներքսագոյնս:

Corals are marine animals, the distinguishing characteristic of which is their durable and intensely colored red or pink-orange skeleton, which is used for making jewelry. In English lingua-culture, the word “coral” is defined as:

1. a hard substance formed in the sea from masses of shells of very small sea animals, usually orange or red;

2. having a color between orange and pink.

As we can see from the definitions of the word, in each meaning the keywords are “red” and “orange”. We have already observed in relation to carbuncle that, red is not only one of the primary colors, but it's also one of the first colors used by artists—dating back to pre-history. [8]

As for the second color of orange, it is a color that provokes an immediate reaction. Bold and dynamic, orange is used to signal danger while at the same time creating a sensation of excitement. Interestingly, in Europe, the color orange didn't have a name until the 16th century. Before that time it was simply called yellow-red. Before the word orange came into common use in English, saffron was sometimes used to describe the deep yellow-orange color. This changed when orange trees were brought to Europe from Asia by Portuguese merchants. The color was then named after the ripe fruit, which carries through many different languages. Orange in English, naranja in Spanish, arancia in Italian, and laranja in Portuguese. [8]

In Armenian lingua-culture, according to one of the explanations of these colors, the color red is taken as a symbol of the blood of the Armenian nation and is chosen as one of the three colors on the flag. Throughout history, the Armenians have struggled much against foreign invasions. The greatest reason was religion. However, being the first Christian country, the Armenians never betrayed their religious beliefs. The worst disaster was the Armenian genocide with 1.5 million innocent victims. The red color is taken to represent the blood of these victims. The orange color symbolizes the creative talents and hard-working nature of the Armenians.

The word “coral”, according to English-Armenian Dictionary (Անգլերեն-հայերեն բառարան) [6: էջ 113], is translated into Armenian as մարջան and կորալ. In Modern Armenian Expositive Dictionary (Արդի հայերենի բացատրական բառարան) [4: էջ 566] the word մարջան has the following meanings:

1. ծովային կենդանի, պոլիպների մի տեսակ

2. այդ կենդանիների կրաղած մարմիններից գոյացած սպիտակ, կարմիր կամ սև գույնի քար, որից հատուկ մշակությամբ զարդարանք են պատրաստում

Observing the way of rendering the word “coral” from English into Armenian մարջան, we can see that here the translator conveyed the word employing full equivalence, as the pragmatic meanings of the source and target language units are the same. [3: p 56-122]

Quite many gemstones of biblical origin differ in semantic characteristics, expressed in a familiar and understandable pattern specific to national identity, the way of thinking, cultural norms, and assumptions. This is due to linguistic reasons (different language systems), and extra-linguistic ones (intercultural differences). Conversely, numerous gemstones of biblical origin find their semantic equivalence beyond biblical frames.

Thus, the Holy Bible has made a strong influence on the languages and maintained its trace in the Armenian and English lingo-culture. In general, Armenian shows a slightly more intensive use of Holy Scripture than English which, apparently, is connected with cultural and historical reasons.

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